

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

POSTTRAUMATIC STRESS DISORDER IN WAR VETERANS: LITERATURE REVIEW ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The main problem of the study is examining mental health issues of war veterans. According to U.S. Department of veterans affairs, National Centers for PTSD, this problem is slightly more common among Veterans than civilians. At some point in their life, 7 out of every 100 Veterans (or 7%) will have PTSD. In the general population, 6 out of every 100 adults (or 6%) will have PTSD in their lifetime. PTSD is also more common among female Veterans (13 out of 100, or 13%) versus male Veterans (6 out of 100, or 6%).

The study of post-traumatic stress disorder has always been a matter of controversy. Many suspected an organic cause. Other researchers questioned the authenticity of the symptoms and suggested that simulation or the search for compensation (compensation neurosis) was the cause in many cases. As a result, for some time, such an idea prevailed that the traumatic event is the cause, and only people with an emotionally unstable personality type, premorbid neurotic conflict and mental illness can develop persistent symptoms. However, the presence of long-term psychological problems in many people who were war participants, victims of aggression, torture, and rape changed these views over time. Today, it is accepted that a psychotraumatic event is the main cause of PTSD. Researchers have found that even psychologically healthy individuals will develop symptoms consistent with PTSD when faced with dire, catastrophic stressors.

Keywords: veterans, war, PTSD, symptoms of PTSD, stress disorder

Literature review analyzing: If humanity has always had wars, it seems natural to assume soldiers have always suffered from PTSD. But PTSD as a recognized diagnosis is relatively new. In fact, PTSD was not added to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual (DSM) until 1980. Since the close of the Vietnam war, journal articles began to question the link between the mental health consequences of having served in Vietnam, crime, and incarceration rates. But those articles didn't yet have the PTSD diagnosis in their analytic arsenal—it simply didn't exist. Now that it does, contemporary articles retroactively apply what we now know as PTSD to centuries-old accounts of veterans suffering mental health issues. To understand the modern discourse around PTSD and incarceration, it is imperative to understand its evolution through history.

From the bible to Greco-Roman classics, tales of soldiers suffering nightmares of battle abound. The etiological conception of wounds on the psyche shifted through the eras, bouncing between physical and emotional causes. There may not have been agreement over its cause or the precise collection of symptoms, but there was a recognition that severe trauma left an indelible mark on the psyches of some exposed people. During both world wars, newspapers ran stories about afflicted soldiers and full military psychiatric hospitals. Yet the multifarious symptoms were not combined into a cohesive disorder. One thing that may have contributed to the delayed diagnosis was the male ethos of stoically enduring pain, which likely prompted hundreds of thousands of combat veterans through America's history to suffer in silence even as medical advancements skyrocketed in the 20th century. "When we got out, you couldn't talk about things like that... You held it all in. I didn't want to take it to my family," World

War Two veteran Otis Mackey told the Washington Post, decades after the war. "If you'd say anything, people wouldn't believe half of what you say, anyway." That said, battle trauma is just the most commonly discussed type of trauma. While what is probably the most commonly occurring form of war trauma, sexual assault, is rarely mentioned. For centuries, too many stories of how women (and some men) responded to rape trauma went untold while soldiers' accounts of struggling with disturbing memories of battle are documented frequently. Pioneering European researchers made great strides towards the recognition of a cohesive disorder in their work treating Holocaust survivors, identifying concentration camp syndrome. When the first DSM was published in 1952, it contained a temporary psychiatric disorder called "gross stress reaction." By the time the second DSM was published in 1968, shortly after the US entered the Vietnam war, even that had been removed. Whether the Veterans Administration wanted to reduce their financial liability to Vietnam veterans or it was truly regarded as a nonspecific and/or nonclinical diagnosis is unclear. For the duration of the Vietnam War, not a single diagnosis relating to stress exposure was ever accepted in the DSM. In the early years of the Vietnam War, VA psychiatrists believed that recent combat veterans displaying neuroses or psychoses were afflicted by something not combat-related, as no combat-related (or even trauma-related) diagnoses were at their disposal. For the same reason, VA disability claims alleging psychological injury as a result of combat were resoundingly denied. Therapists at the VA avoided talking with their patients about what had occurred overseas since the dominant belief was that couldn't be to blame for their psychological disturbance.

Pockets of disgruntled veterans formed mutual aid groups in response. One such group was the Twice-Born Men for Vietnam veterans coming out of prison. From providing a forum to discuss the horrors of war to practical job-seeking assistance, the groups brought veterans together to help other veterans. Some engaged in advocacy, including trying to get a combat syndrome included in the then-forthcoming DSM as a new diagnosis.

Through the concerted effort of advocates, psychiatrists, psychiatrist-advocates, and a burgeoning base of empirical research, the APA's resistance to including the new disorder waned. The definition and diagnostic criteria were determined in a workgroup, but its inclusion in the DSM was opposed by some psychiatrists on the grounds that depression, schizophrenia, and alcoholism sufficiently covered the disorders experienced by Vietnam and prior war veterans.

The decade preceding the inclusion of the PTSD diagnosis in the DSM marked a period of deinstitutionalization of psychiatric facilities in the United States. The shift towards community-based care, which often resulted in closures of state hospitals, has been criticized. Ample bodies of scholarly work illuminate the correlation between the dismantling of state psychiatric facilities and an increase in the prison population. It was into this landscape that millions of veterans were returning.

In total, the United States sent 2.7 million people abroad to fight in Vietnam, 700,000 of whom needed some form of psychological treatment. The sheer number of traumatized veterans attempting to reintegrate into their communities was staggering. Prior to the PTSD diagnosis, they could receive neither proper treatment nor a disability pension from the Veterans Administration. Then in 1980, the DSM-III was published and included the recently-identified condition of PTSD. Finally, veterans had a phrase for what they had been experiencing. They also had a right to compensation.

The organization Vietnam Veterans of America (VVA) published repeatedly in the Long Line Writer, a prison newspaper produced in the Arkansas Department of Corrections Cummins Unit. They report being inundated by requests for assistance from veterans incarcerated across the country. The organization maintained membership in the American Correctional Association and created a "Veterans Incarcerated Committee." Clearly, the need for care was great.

In a May 2000 issue of the Long Line Writer, Joseph Breault writes, "VVA believes that past trauma is a complicating factor in the lives of many veterans incarcerated. Some veterans' crimes and incarceration may be attributable (at least in part) to this condition." Later in the same article the author included the 1990 testimony of Representative George Brown before the House Judiciary Committee.

There is a correlation between PTSD and an increased risk of incarceration. Irritable behavior and unprovoked angry outbursts, along with reckless and self-destructive behavior, are all among the diagnostic criteria. In certain circumstances, these can manifest as behaviors that constitute crimes. PTSD is a risk factor

in developing a substance use disorder, which is a risk factor for experiencing incarceration, other behaviors aside. As stated in a 2019 American Journal of Psychology article, "The most recent (2011-2012) government statistics suggest that veterans compose approximately 8% of the prison population... Other studies present accounts of service members and veterans exhibiting increased tendencies for aggressive, violent, or criminal behavior after returning home from overseas deployments."

PTSD is now one of the most commonly rated disabilities by the Veterans Administration. The theory underpinning veteran disability compensation is that if a service member was injured in service to their country, the country is then obligated to compensate them for that injury as long as they continue to suffer it. A natural extension of this philosophy would be accounting for PTSD's influence on behavior if those behaviors should result in criminal convictions.

The historical impact that veterans have had on psychiatric advancement is often overlooked. Trauma-informed care is now the gold standard of medical treatment while a few decades ago the mere existence of trauma was doubted by medical professionals. How society identifies and addresses PTSD has undergone a cataclysmic shift in the past forty years. The 1980 addition of the disorder into the DSM-III had far-reaching implications that spanned well beyond the military and Veterans Administration. The influence of PTSD on behaviors that may constitute crimes is being studied. What other institutions might be influenced by the expanded understanding of trauma's lasting effects is yet to be seen. When academia and advocacy coalesce, societal change is possible.

Secondary Traumatic Stress (STS) is a term used to describe the consequent behaviours and emotions resulting from exposure to a traumatizing event which occurred to a person the individual is close to (Figley, 1995). Figley and McCubbin (1983) initially termed this phenomenon secondary catastrophic stress reaction, emphasizing emotional upset, exhaustion, vigilance, and avoidance that commonly characterize this condition. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5; American Psychiatric Association, 2013) has acknowledged secondary traumatization as one possible diagnostic criterion for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Importantly, aside from the difference in the triggering circumstances of the disorder, the symptoms of STS are believed to be identical to those of PTSD (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Thus, STS and PTSD might be very similar if not identical. While STS has been studied mainly in children or spouses of traumatized individuals, the current study focuses on STS in parents of war veterans.

That trauma can be transferred to spouses, therapists, and mainly children of individuals who experienced a traumatic event, has been demonstrated in several seminal investigations (Dinshtein et al., 2011; Weinberg et al., 2016). One study (Tehrani, 2007) found that over 60% of therapists who treated traumatized clients experienced STS symptoms, including a feeling that they will not be able to recover from their

exposure to the traumatic event. Within families, some studies have focused on transmission of trauma from one spouse to the other (Solomon et al., 1992), while most investigations focused on the transmission of trauma from parents to their children. For example, recent studies reported STS symptoms in adult children (Shrira, 2015), and even grandchildren (Letzter-Pouw et al., 2014) of Holocaust survivors, decades after the Holocaust. Similarly, Zerach and Aloni (2015) found significant STS symptoms among children of former prisoners of war (see also Zerach et al., 2017). Furthermore, the research on the mechanism behind the transmission of trauma is also mainly focused on how trauma is transferred from parents to offspring (before and after the child is born). Several studies suggested that maternal exposure to stress and trauma during pregnancy might have negative physiological and psychological effects on the offspring (O'Connor et al., 2013; Shrira, 2015). Recently, Yehuda and Lehner (2018) conducted a comprehensive review that emphasised the in-utero changes that might be mediated by maternal trauma-related symptoms. This accumulating evidence emphasises the notion that emotionally charged relationships with a traumatised person may lead to the transmission of trauma. It also suggests that more research is required to fully understand how trauma is transmitted.

Neglecting the effect of traumatized veterans on their parents' well-being, is an outstanding gap in the literature, which is especially noticeable given that young adults are more likely to actively participate in military conflicts while their parents anxiously await their return. While we have learned relatively more about the effect of war on the mental well-being of soldiers, veterans, spouses, children, and therapists (e.g. Canfield, 2005; Dagan et al., 2016; Tehrani, 2007), we know very little about the psychological effect of these traumatic situations on the parents of war veterans. Not only should such information be heavily considered as part of the 'cost of war', but it would also have very specific implications for countries mental health policies regarding parents of war veterans. Importantly, just as traumatized parents return to live with their children and spouses, young adults often return to live with their parents after the traumatizing experience, at least for a few years. Given that parents may be especially attuned to their children's negative experiences, the exposure of a child's traumatic symptoms or traumatic stories may serve as an additional stressor to parents on top of the already stressful war. Thus, parents of war veterans might be an overlooked at-risk group for the development of STS symptoms or even PTSD.

Bazini M. and Konstantopoulou G. searched this problem examining various of published materials and summarized it. The authors examined that in the difference between the two genders - males and females, it appears sometimes that high prevalence predominates in the former, sometimes in the latter, and sometimes that they have relatively similar levels of prevalence. According to Ovuga et al (2008), report that boys, are more likely to be exposed toward traumatic events but less likely to receive psychological support, perhaps linking this to the social demands for a specific male

gender profile regarding emotions. Khaleel Al-Doori (2020), like Perkins et al. (2018), report a higher prevalence in women, with the latter defining female gender as a factor in the disorder as well. However, Goldberg et al. (2015) and Wolf et al. (2013), report relatively similar rates of the disorder among male and female veterans (Bazini M. and Konstantopoulou G., 2023). During the study Bazini and colleague noted that the differences in prevalence records between the sexes are the result of many factors. One factor may be social reality and existing gender 'norms' in different cultures. These norms may result in men not expressing themselves as they would like by showing their feelings. Women, on the other hand, have identified with the gender that shows more of their emotional state, and may have found it easier, to perform on the relevant diagnostic tests that measured symptomatology. PTSD is associated with being in war and is shown by the prevalence of the disorder in the general population, in children and youth and in military veterans, which is at a high rate. As shown by comparisons between population groups, the general population, children and youth, appear to have the highest rates of the disorder. Veterans while having the lowest, as shown in Table 3, still comprise a non-negligible percentage of the population. The only exception is the study by Frueh et al. (2009), in which the rate is extremely low, but, as the results show, studies a rarer type of PTSD. In response to the question of whether PTSD is associated with war with the three population groups selected, the results are in the affirmative to the question.

There are special items that were trigger for stress disorders. Factors recorded were occupation (Abu-El-Noor, 2020a; 2020b), being a parent (Seino et al., 2008), location of the war, such as Syria and Vietnam, type of trauma, conscription (Betancourt et al., 2013), as was evident, at a young age, perhaps gender, income (Khaleel & Al-Doori, 2020), parental education (Khaleel & Al-Doori, 2020), social and cultural identity (Burri & Maercker, 2014; Shaar, 2013), mental health of relatives (Ovuga et al., 2008) and the place where the main war events take place (Goldberg et al., 2015 & Magruder et al., 2015)

Treatment models: The following psychotherapy approaches are strongly recommended by either the American Psychological Association (APA.org) or the U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs (VA.gov) as PTSD treatment options.

- Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT): This approach emphasizes how thoughts, feelings, and actions influence one another. The goal is to develop new patterns of thoughts, emotions, and behaviors pertaining to the traumatic experience and related subjects. Cognitive therapy, a related approach, focuses specifically on altering painful memories and evaluations related to the trauma that hinder daily functioning.

- Cognitive Processing Therapy (CPT): This modality aims to help individuals develop new, more helpful understandings of their traumatic experiences through critical reflection.

- Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR): This form of therapy involves recalling the trauma while paying attention to a back-and-forth movement or sound controlled by the clinician.
- Prolonged Exposure (PE): This approach emphasizes incrementally challenging negative feelings and altering patterns of avoidance stemming from one's trauma.

Other therapeutic interventions may also prove effective in specific cases, so please seek the clinical expertise of a mental health professional if you are interested in learning more. Appropriate clinicians to contact regarding PTSD treatment include counselors, social workers, psychologists, psychiatrists, and nurse practitioners specializing in psychiatry.

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